

Workshop: Reframing Crash Course: How to design meaningful citizenship?

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Topic The rise of active citizenship marks the transition from a welfare society to a participation society. So-called third generation citizens' participation indicates that the relation between government and society has flipped: the civil society initiates, the government participates (Lenos, Sturm & Vis, 2006). However, third generation participation appears to be problematic in its execution. Various questions arise, for instance: How to engage all citizens, is this possible and/or desirable?

Although Social Economic Status (SES) explains participation to a large extent (Verba et al., 1995), in general it is self-confidence to play a key role: "The *self-confident* citizen is likely to be the *active* citizen" (Almond & Verba, 1963/1989). In other words: engagement requires self-confidence. Hence, the Reframing Crash Course will take self-confidence as a starting point to design meaningful citizenship in the future.

By using the renowned *reframing process**, the Crash Course inspires participants to let go of the 'here and now' and to apply the tools provided to anticipate the future of citizenship. Reframing is firmly rooted in a consciously constructed – future – world. It goes through specific steps and several phases that provide a clear design trajectory for each project. Since the process defines the goal and not the means, the method can be applied to broader, multi-stakeholder and societal topics such as citizens' participation.

* The reframing process is based on the Vision in Product design (ViP) method, which has been developed at the Delft University of Technology by Prof. Ir. Matthijs van Dijk and Prof. dr. Paul Hekkert.

Purpose

The aim of the Crash Course is to:

1. Experience the reframing process;
2. Explore the future context of citizenship;
3. Enjoy collaborating in a cross-disciplinary context.

As reframing focuses on value patterns and design relations rather than products, its process is particularly fit for the purpose of analyzing human behavior and societal relations.

Keywords *Citizenship, Design thinking, Engagement, Reframing, Self-confidence*